

The new GTN-P Data Platform: global long-term permafrost observations

Authors:

Tillmann Lübker, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, tillmann.luebker@awi.de

Anna Irrgang, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, anna.irrgang@awi.de

Sebastian Laboor, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, sebastian.laboor@awi.de

Guido Grosse, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, University of Potsdam, guido.grosse@awi.de

Hugues Lantuit, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, University of Potsdam, hugues.lantuit@awi.de

Dmitry Streletskiy, George Washington University, strelets@gwu.edu

The Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P, <https://www.gtn-p.org>), established in the late 1990s, is the primary international program for long-term permafrost monitoring. Its mission is to sustain a comprehensive global network that delivers consistent, high-quality observations of key permafrost indicators, enabling assessment of its current state and evolution over time. GTN-P operates under a robust governance structure with strategic oversight by a Steering Committee and Advisory Board, coordinated through the GTN-P Office at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI, Permafrost Research Unit Potsdam). The network is further supported by 36 National Correspondents and 14 Young National Correspondents, who coordinate data contributions across all permafrost regions.

GTN-P supports GCOS and UNFCCC observational requirements and is recognized by international organizations, global observing systems, and the scientific community. Permafrost is a key land-cryosphere Essential Climate Variable (ECV), with core measurements capturing changes that affect climate, ecosystems, and infrastructure. The network currently serves the two Permafrost ECV quantities, Permafrost Temperature (PT) and Active Layer Thickness (ALT), with contributions from scientists in over thirty countries, consolidated into a central database with rigorous coordination, standardization, and quality control.

The new **GTN-P Data Platform** (<https://data.gtn-p.org>), launched in January 2026, was developed through extensive community consultation and represents a major step forward in data management and accessibility. The platform allows users to explore data availability, access standardized metadata, and visualize time series of temperature-depth profiles. Emphasis was placed on a clear and intuitive interface to facilitate both scientific and broader stakeholder use. In a dedicated upload section, registered users can submit measurement data and manage associated metadata. Drop-down lists, controlled vocabularies, and an integrated help system ensure consistency and reduce errors, while preview and automated validation checks further enhance data quality.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the GTN-P Data Platform presenting global long-term permafrost observation data.

The infrastructure is entirely hosted at the AWI Computing and Data Center and is designed for long-term reliability, scalability, and maintainability. All components are containerized and run in virtualized environments to ensure reproducible deployments and simplified maintenance. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) have been introduced for sites, datasets, and related resources, providing stable and permanent references. An identifier resolver translates PID requests into standard web queries and returns content in multiple formats: CSV for raw data, JSON for structured metadata, and HTML for human-readable pages. A public API allows programmatic access to both data and metadata, thus supporting interoperability with other data systems and tools. Together, these features make the Data Platform a modern, reliable, and user-friendly tool for managing, sharing, and utilizing global permafrost data.

True interoperability requires not only technical access but also formal standardization of data and metadata. For public environmental data, initiatives such as the European INSPIRE directive ensure standardized formats and vocabularies. For scientific data, such harmonization is less common. Against this backdrop, a group of technical and domain experts under the WMO Global Cryosphere Watch is currently working to develop a formalized standard for PT and ALT data based on CF-NetCDF profiles. **We argue that such community-driven efforts are essential to enable true data interoperability and can serve as a roadmap for other Arctic science-driven data domains.**

The GTN-P database currently comprises more than 20 million data points, including approximately 275,000 annually measured ALT values, alongside metadata for 1,487 boreholes and 255 ALT sites. Together, these data form a substantial resource of permafrost observations. Yet datasets are currently available for only about 30% of known PT sites and 41% of known ALT sites. Apart from adding such still missing datasets, spatial coverage could be further improved by including historical inactive sites as well as active monitoring sites currently not yet included in the database. With the previous database system reaching the limits of its original technical design, submissions had slowed. **We argue that the new GTN-P Data Platform provides a timely opportunity to re-energize and strengthen the network by providing a highly visible, modern permafrost community data platform and facilitating the contribution of existing and newly acquired data, enhancing both coverage and long-term value.**

The GTN-P Office, hosted at AWI since 2011, together with the recently established Data Platform, has been supported through a series of third-party funded research projects. While this model has enabled substantial development of coordination and data services, no long-term, direct funding is currently available. A similar situation applies to many national permafrost monitoring programmes, which often rely on short-term research funding despite long-term observational mandates. **We argue that sustained support for core operations is essential to ensure continuity, reliability, and ongoing operational capacity of the network, and to safeguard the lasting value of its data and services for the scientific community and broader stakeholders.**